

AUDITORY ELECTROPHYSIOLOGY: EVERYTHING YOU NEED TO KNOW BEFORE STARTING YOUR ASSESSMENTS (PART III) – NUMBER OF SOUND STIMULUS AVERAGES

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The purpose of this bulletin is to help you learn more about the important theoretical and technical factors required to develop effective electrophysiological assessment methods. Before proceeding, we ask you to read Part I (released in March 2025), which addresses a fundamental mathematical concept commonly used in the auditory evoked potential field: standard deviations. We also refer you to a newsletter published in May 2025 that reports on selecting stimulus polarity (rarefaction, condensation, or alternating) in diagnostic auditory evoked response measurement. Continuing this series, the current issue focuses on the quantity of averaged sound stimuli.

Fortunately, there are numerous guidelines available today that provide valuable information on the best test parameter settings for conducting auditory electrophysiological investigations. The clinical guidelines and publications that we reviewed in the development of this paper are listed in the references section.

IMPEDANCE ANALYSIS AND CONTROL

Before auditory electrophysiologic measurement begins, an adequately low inter-electrode impedance (< 5000 ohms) must be verified. As the averaging process begins and the number of stimulus rejections is high (> 10%), then the evaluator must reassess electrode locations and impedances before continuing further. Other possible sources of excessive measurement artifact include electrical interference and myogenic (muscle) artifact associated with patient movement.

ARTIFACT LEVEL VERSUS NUMBER OF AVERAGED STIMULI

The extent of measurement artifact control will have an overall impact on the quality of auditory electrophysiologic responses. Small amplitude and high-frequency aberrations, whether from electrical or myogenic sources, make it difficult to accurately analyze response components (waves). Excessive distortion interferes with precise identification of wave peaks, a requirement for correctly calculating latencies.

An evaluator needs to consider the number of stimuli that are required for satisfactory measurement (e.g., British Society of Audiology, 2019; British Society of Audiology, 2025). If the patient is calm throughout the test, then averaging 2000 stimuli per wave is usually sufficient to produce minimal measurement noise. Under favorable measurement conditions, it is often possible to record with even fewer stimulus repetitions. The aim is a robust, clear, and reliable response with low residual noise. An optimal measurement scenario includes auditory responses evoked with a high intensity click or a high frequency tone burst from patients with normal hearing sensitivity, ideally sleeping naturally or with the assistance of sedation or anesthesia. Conversely, an evaluator should consider extending the averaging process, i.e., increasing the number of stimulus presentations whenever artifact rejection levels exceed $\pm 10 \mu\text{V}$ ($> 10\%$ rejection).

The quadratic law can be applied to determine how many stimuli to use and how much artifact rejection is required. A doubling of the artifact rejection level requires triple the number of triggered stimuli (Lightfoot and Stevens 2014). To ensure a successful examination, use the following scheme.

Table 1: Correlation between artifact rejection level and number of auditory stimuli (Lightfoot & Stevens, 2014).

Artifact rejection level	Number of stimuli elicited (click or chirp)
±5 µV	2000
±10 µV	4000
±20 µV	8000

Evaluators should reflect on this important information: the use of a fixed number of elicited stimuli is often not the most appropriate strategy for optimal auditory evoked response measurement.

Two undesirable test outcomes are likely if the evaluator consistently presents a fixed number of averaged stimuli without considering the artifact rejection level. Under adverse measurement conditions, with excessive artifact rejection, it is very likely that an inconclusive waveform will be recorded. However, when an auditory electrophysiologic response is recorded with a fixed number under optimal measurement conditions, the test time may be unnecessarily lengthened. The evaluator must also recognize that the number of averaged stimuli varies according to the type of sound stimulus (e.g., click versus tone burst, high- versus low-frequency tone burst, traditional vs. chirp stimuli).

EVALUATIONS WITH DIFFERENT NUMBERS OF STIMULI

A good collection strategy must be followed, especially for neurodiagnostic click-evoked auditory brainstem response assessments, which are measures of auditory pathway function. This is because ABR latencies, amplitudes, and interpeak intervals need to be marked accurately.

Figure 1 shows waveforms for a neurodiagnostic ABR assessment with click-type stimuli conducted on two females aged 21 (exam A) and 32 years (exam B). We conducted the exams at an intensity of 80 dBnNA, varying the number of stimuli and ensuring the repeatability of the waves in each condition. The six evaluation conditions and the different numbers of averaged stimuli were:

1st condition: 120 stimuli.

2nd condition: 250 stimuli.

3rd condition: 500 stimuli.

4th condition: 1000 stimuli.

5th condition: 1500 stimuli.

6th condition: 2000 stimuli.

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It is interesting to note that in exam A there is satisfactory reproducibility of the waves with 1000 to 1500 averaged stimuli. Whereas in exam B, the ABR has good reproducibility of the waves with as few as 500 to 1000 averaged stimuli. These ABR data show that there is variability in responses among different individuals. Evaluators need to be attentive to the recording parameters used and how they can influence each response.

According to the BSA recommendations (British Society of Audiology, 2025), no waveform should contain fewer than 1000 averaged stimuli. However, under optimal measurement conditions, a reliable ABR may be recorded with as few as 500 stimuli. Nevertheless, the evaluator must make this decision with deliberate intention.

It is clinically important to mention that the presence of high levels of artifacts with a reduced number of elicited auditory stimuli can lead to the following impairments:

- **Overlap:** High-frequency artifacts can overlap with wave peaks, distorting their shape and making them difficult to distinguish from background noise.
- **Displacement:** The presence of artifacts can lead to errors in identifying wave peaks with compromised accuracy of latency calculations.
- **Masking:** In more severe cases, artifacts can completely mask wave peaks, preventing their identification and analysis.

Figure 1: ABR measurement conducted with two female individuals aged 21 (A) and 32 (B) years, respectively. ABRs were recorded using the NeuroAudio equipment and the Neurosoft model. In exam A, all waves are evident and have good reproducibility, starting with 1500 stimulus presentations. In exam B, all waves become evident and have good reproducibility with 500 stimulus presentations.

Another significant ABR measurement factor that must be considered is the robustness of the V wave. Confident identification of wave V requires an amplitude more than three times the amplitude of residual noise. The following calculation is worth noting:

$$\text{Signal-to-noise (SNR)} = \frac{\text{Signal Amplitude} \times \text{Number of Averages}}{\text{Noise Amplitude}}$$

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With the signal corresponding to the ABR the noise consisting of any electrical activity that is not ABR (e.g, ambient electrical artifact, myogenic activity, EEG).

F STATISTICAL INDEX (SIGNAL-TO-NOISE RATIO)

There is a way to confidently record ABRs with a minimal number of stimulus averages. For this, it is essential that the evaluator have access to objective measurement tools that meet the recommended criteria for 97% or more confidence in the presence of responses. With ABR equipment that includes objective analysis features, an evaluator can confidently conclude the assessment before reaching the previously calculated number of stimulus presentations. One example of a clinical objective measurement approach is the Fsp or Fmp (F statistics for single points or multiple points) which statistically differentiates the ABR versus residual noise (Elberling and Don, 1984).

The Fsp statistical index quantifies the relationship between the variance of a sample of the averaged electrophysiological data which includes the magnitude of the ABR, the residual background noise, and the variance of the background noise itself. In essence, the Fsp acts as an indicator of the true ABR in relation to noise. High Fsp values reflect an ABR with greater magnitude compared to background noise, providing greater confidence in identifying the response.

Don and Elberling (1994) proposed an evolution of the Fsp, called Fmp, which is distinguished by the analysis of multiple points along the waveform instead of a single point. This multi-point approach allows for a more comprehensive and accurate assessment of the signal-to-noise ratio.

Some clinical ABR devices use Fsp and others use Fmp. Evaluators are advised to identify whether these tools are available as features on their ABR systems. The British Society of Audiology guidelines (British Society of Audiology, 2025) recommended use of criteria for Fsp/Fmp with 97% or more confidence. The following table compares F statistics for ABR equipment with manufacturers listed in alphabetical order:

Table 2: Recommended criteria for Fsp/Fmp measurements with 97% or greater confidence in the presence of a response.

Equipment	Recommended criteria for Fsp/Fmp with 97% or more confidence in the presence of response
Biologic	Do not use
Interacoustic Eclipse (software version 4.6.1 or later) by Lightfoot et al., 2023	> 2.2
Interacoustic Eclipse (software version 4.4 or earlier)	Do not use
Neurosoft NeuroAudio (report ERA Training)	> 2.5
Vivosonic Integrity V500 (Manufacturer specifications, version 8.12.0 or later)	> 1.25

It is important for the evaluator to be aware of the need for wave repeatability to ensure that the generated responses are indeed valid.

RESIDUAL NOISE LEVEL

Another useful tool for objective analysis of ABR measurements is ongoing monitoring of residual noise levels. Monitoring should occur throughout the evaluation process. Each evaluation system has a target value that must be reached during the averaging of a response to repeated stimulus presentations. Observe Figure 2 below how this analysis appears on the equipment screen. As the number of stimuli presented increases, there should be a corresponding decrease in the noise level. Typically, values differ for pediatric versus adult patients. Essentially, the lower the level of residual noise, the more reliable the obtained response.

Figure 2: Neurosoft NeuroAudio equipment

WHAT COULD HAPPEN WHEN THIS NOISE LEVEL REMAINS HIGH, RATHER THAN DECREASING WITH A HIGHER NUMBER OF STIMULUS PRESENTATIONS?

1. The waveform may take longer before good reproducibility is achieved;
2. Noise can obscure the response;
3. Response reliability is decreased;
4. It is difficult to visualize the waves;
5. Response measurement should not be interrupted if the criterion for selecting the residual noise level is not met.

As mentioned earlier, manufacturers of different devices available on the market offer this feature in their ABR systems. The British Society of Audiology guidelines recommendation (British Society of Audiology, 2025) include recommendations for criteria (target values) for residual noise measures. Criteria are summarized below, with equipment manufacturers listed in alphabetical order:

Table 3: Recommended criteria for the use of residual noise measurements across different devices

Equipament	Recommended target value
Biologic	30nV
GSI Audera Pro	120nV
Interacoustic Eclipse (software version 4.2 or earlier)	50nV
Interacoustic Eclipse (software version 4.4.2 or later)	30nV
Neurosoft NeuroAudio	34nV
Vivosonic Integrity V500	40nV

It should be noted that the residual noise values, if available on a device, can be used as a guide for interrupting ABR measurement in patients suspected of having no responses (see the table below).

Table 4: Guidelines for the use of residual noise measurements across various devices

Equipament	Recommended target value
Biologic	15nV
GSI Audera Pro	60nV
Interacoustic Eclipse (software version 4.2 or earlier)	25nV
Interacoustic Eclipse (software version 4.4.2 or later)	15nV
Neurosoft NeuroAudio	17nV
Vivosonic Integrity V500	20nV

Objective measurement tools such as Fsp/Fmp and noise level can help the evaluator determine when to end data collection, especially in the case of neurodiagnostic evaluation. However, the repeatability of the waveform is always essential.

TRADITIONAL CLICK STIMULI VERSUS BROADBAND CHIRP STIMULI

In an interesting study, Stuart and Cobb (2014) compared ABRs using traditional click-type stimuli versus ABRs using broadband chirp-type stimuli. The original chirp stimuli are described as CE-chirps, with reference to the developer (Claus Elberling). The study included ABRs elicited with varied numbers of stimuli, e.g., 116, 233, 464, 958, and 1856. Stimulus and collection parameters were similar to those used in neonatal hearing screening with automated ABR. Wave V amplitudes were significantly higher in all collection conditions performed with the CE-Chirp. Also, ABR wave V was visualized with a smaller number of stimuli with the CE-Chirp stimulus as compared to the traditional click stimulus. Wave V was visualized with around 464 stimuli with the CE-Chirp stimulus versus 1856 stimuli with the traditional click stimulus. Results are similar for ABRs recorded from adults. The larger and more robust amplitude of wave V is related to compensation of the temporal delay associated with activation of different frequency regions in the cochlea. CE-Chirp stimuli are most useful for electrophysiologic estimation of auditory thresholds, but they can also be applied in assessment of the integrity of the auditory pathways.

TRADITIONAL TONE BURST STIMULI VERSUS NARROWBAND CHIRP STIMULI

Tone burst stimuli are necessary for objective frequency-specific estimation of auditory thresholds, that is, an electrophysiological audiogram. The results of earlier studies suggested that low frequency tone burst stimuli are less precise than high frequency stimuli in estimating behavioral auditory thresholds (Picton et al., 1979; Hayes and Jerger, 1982). However, more recent investigations confirm that ABRs elicited with tone burst stimuli provide a reasonably accurate estimate of behavioral thresholds.

Amplitudes of ABRs recorded with tone burst stimuli are sometimes smaller than those for click-type stimuli. Some researchers note that the ABR acquisition time with tone burst stimulation can be up to twice as long as the time for click stimulation, since a greater number of stimuli are needed for an adequate visualization of reliable waveforms.

Considering the larger amplitudes for ABRs elicited with broadband and narrowband chirp stimulation versus traditional click and tone burst stimulation, the use of chirp stimuli is preferable for pediatric applications in which efficiency, i.e., brief test time, is a high priority.

COMMENTS

We strongly recommend that evaluators review published auditory evoked response guidelines to deepen their knowledge and stay up-to-date on current best practices.

We invite you to follow us in our new publications for more detailed information.

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